

INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION FOR A BETTER MANAGEMENT OF COVID-19 FOR AN EVENTUAL GROWTH

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ABSTRACT

Background

The Coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic declared as a public health emergency of international concern by WHO has created a rapid and changing healthcare landscape that has impacted communication amongst individuals and even in communities all over the globe.

Objectives

The objective of our research was to identify the different methods and strategies of communication used to maintain the transmission of the right information concerning Covid-19 pandemic so as to create a non-Covid-19 environment and the possible actors implicated.

Methods

A review was conducted using PubMed, Google scholar, Hinari and Google on articles published between 2021 and 2023 that illustrated both some management tips of communication and information on covid-19.

Results

Out of 15 sources collected that had a link with our research, only 10 were retained for our review. Social media like Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, Tencent, YouTube, Tweeter and to a certain extent WhatsApp were the major one used. Also, good information given by different actors while using good communication strategies like online debates, videos with attractive pictures and music,

posters with pictures and noted warnings, education and sensibilization were the main point as sited by different authors in the management of Covid-19.

Conclusion

The Covid-19 pandemic thought us a lot. Information and good communication strategies are the major steps to improve on the management of situation and also ameliorate the health of individuals, leading to an eventual growth.

Key words: Information, Communication, Management, Covid-19.

RÉSUMÉ

Contexte

La pandémie de coronavirus (Covid-19), déclarée urgence de santé publique de portée internationale par l'OMS, a créé un paysage sanitaire rapide et changeant qui a eu un impact sur la communication entre les individus et même au sein des communautés du monde entier.

Objectifs de l'étude

L'objectif de notre recherche était d'identifier les différentes méthodes et stratégies de communication utilisées pour maintenir la transmission des bonnes informations concernant la pandémie de Covid-19 afin de créer un environnement sans Covid-19 et les acteurs possibles impliqués.

Méthodes utilisées

Une revue a été réalisée à l'aide de PubMed, Google Scholar, Hinari et Google sur les articles publiés entre 2021 et 2023 qui illustrent à la fois quelques conseils de gestion de la communication et de l'information sur le covid-19.

Résultats

Sur les 15 sources collectées ayant un lien avec notre recherche, seules 10 ont été retenues pour notre revue. Les médias sociaux telle que Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, Tencent, YouTube et dans certaines mesure WhatsApp ont été les plus utilisées. En outre, des informations de qualité données par différents acteurs en utilisant de bonnes stratégies de communication telles que des débats téléviser en ligne, des vidéos avec des images et de la musique attrayante, des affiches avec des images et des avertissements, l'éducation et la sensibilisation ont été les principaux points cités par différents auteurs dans la gestion de la Covid-19.

Conclusion

La Covid-19 nous as beaucoup appris. L'information et la communication sont des enjeux majeurs pour faire une bonne gestion des situations et par l'amélioré, la santé des individus et par la suite amène une croissance éventuelle.

Mots Clés : Information, Communication, Gestion, Covid-19.

INTRODUCTION:

The Coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic has created a rapid and changing healthcare landscape that has impacted communication among individuals and in communities all over the globe. It was actually declared a public health emergency of international concern by the World Health Organization (WHO) on January 2020 (Elaine Wittenberg et al., 2020).

WHO declared the COVID-19 outbreak as a pandemic on 11 March 2020. Since the upcoming of the said pandemic Covid-19, all countries around the world have been using strategies in one way or the other to tackle and control the spread of infection in their countries in particular, thereby reducing in the number of infected persons globally. COVID-19 pandemic exposed people to psychological distress, fatigue, occupational burnout, fear, stigma therefore it is of utmost importance the effective communication should be ensured at workplace, families and communities. Responding to COVID-19 requires critical preparedness and response which includes effective communication as an essential strategy. Communication is a mode of the imparting or exchanging of messages by speaking, writing, or using some other medium. During a pandemic, communication is not only conveying messages to people but has a much wider approach (B Venkatashiva Reddy & Arti Gupta, 2020).

Globally, the number of confirmed cases is approximately 762 791 152, whereby we observe approximately 6 897 025 deaths and 13 340 275 493 vaccine doses. In Africa on the other hand, we observe 5 continents that were mostly affected by Covid-19 whereby, approximately 8 981 388 were confirmed cases, 174 211 are number of death cases. In Cameroon, the number of cumulative cases are 124 834 (1,39% of all the cases in the region). The attack rate was observed to be 447,68 per 100.000 population, with a number of cumulative death of 1970 death (with a cumulative frequency of 1,58%). The number of cumulative recovered was observed to be 122 762 (98,34% of cumulative cases) (WHO, 2023).

This pandemic significantly changed people's lifestyles by imposing new measures and for most people unacceptable and not easily enforceable. The globally COVID-19 Pandemic caused fear first and foremost for people's health, their lives, and then numerous financial problems for families, communities, firms, corporations and governments as a whole. This deepened the panic

of the society by imposing insecurity for any kind of social action taken by the different states. There are a number of studies that have been dedicated to the impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic in every sphere of life including economy, social, health, education and many other aspects, which have a direct or indirect link with the life situation of individuals. The main focus of this study is to bring out the different contributions of actors that have to contribute to a non Covid-19 environment, with different sources of communication and information techniques or processes.

Information and communication are key aspects when it comes to dealing with situations, especially concerning the health of individuals. The information that are send indifferent areas around the globe will be taking into consideration and will be applicable in all communities. The WHO make sure all the information to be send concerning the health of individuals in the world is really sectioned, well organized, and has a direct positive impact for the population. A proper information will guarantee the wellbeing of individuals. What is to be said is of great importance. An excessive amount of information about the COVID-19 pandemic was spread widely. While some information was true, much on the other hand was false. This resulted in misinformation and misunderstanding, thereby creating enormous rumors in communities. The communication process, on the other hand will have a great influence on the information. Communication is all about attending a particular set of individuals, using certain channels, making sure the medium of communication is fluid, free and reaches both terminals (sender and receiver). The availability of information during the Covid-19 pandemic was really in a great amount whereby different channels of communication showed what it was all about. But what were really the different method of communication and strategies used to maintain a correct information about Covid-19 in order to create a non Covid-19 environment by which actors intervene in one way or the other?

METHODOLOGY:

The main focus of this study is to bring out the different contributions of actors that have to contribute to a non Covid-19 environment, with different sources of communication and information techniques or processes. For this purpose, we went through PubMed, Google, Google Scholar and Hinari between 2021 and 2023 to get different authors who had to do about both information and communication in their articles. In total, we collected 15 articles that had a link with what we were interested in, and at the end, after a thorough and critical reading of the different articles, we retained 10 of the articles which has enable to bring out this present article.

The analyses were being performed through a critical and thorough reading of all the articles collected and only those with interest to our focus of study were retained to bring out our results and discussion.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

B. Venkatesh Reddy & Arti Gupta, (2020) in their study entitled “Importance of effective communication during Covid-19 infodemic” showed us that regarding health risk and danger on vulnerable groups, the impact of Covid-19 relies greatly on the quality of the life conditions, their cultural values and risk experience before taking any action. For them, ignorance of sociocultural, economic, psychological and other health factors could probably jeopardize good communication outputs at all levels. They summarized the framework for effective communication during Covid-19 pandemic. For them, effective communication network is a vital key to assure therapeutic relationships between physicians and health care workers and equally to address the psychology of individuals. According to them, if effective communication is ignored, this will expose vulnerable populations, thus, increasing cases of the pandemic and rendering it’s eradication difficult.

Social media usage has increased manifold and thus, has a number of available platforms, including Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, Instagram, Snapchat, WhatsApp, and Reddit, along with their Chinese equivalents WeChat, Weibo, Tencent, Tik Tok, and Toutiao. People have become accustomed to posting every aspect of their lives on social media. This includes their achievements, worries, and travels on a daily base.

Anwar et al., (2020) in their study precise the fact that, CDC's many beneficial guidelines for preventing COVID-19 were reinforced among people through prominent advertisements on commonly used social media platforms. Facebook, Instagram, and television media posted the importance of 'social distancing' and 'stay at home' through free of cost and frequent, widespread ads. The printed media was utilized by supermarkets to promote their stores following the social distancing protocols. This repetition is essential to consolidate the role of them in preventing the disease spread. This campaign was run extraordinarily by the media using all resources and its subtypes. Also, they came up with the fact that media is the primary source of information and plays a vital role in educating the masses. However, when overly eager sources spread information without proper verification, not only can it be harmful but it can have unintended consequences.

Calleja et al., (2021) brought up the notion management of infodemic in their study entitled "A Public Health Research Agenda for Managing Infodemics: Methods and Results of the First WHO Infodemiology Conference". Here they take into consideration of the fact that, when information is not really gotten or reached to a standard, especially when they are in much quantities, it will not be of great importance or used. The concept of infodemics has to deal with information, both good or bad, wrong or right, at a particular moment. The conference was a great importance since it has to bring out the different tips on how to deal with the information to make it right especially in times of epidemics and pandemics.

In the article published by (Hyland-Wood et al., 2021) title "Toward effective government communication strategies in the era of COVID-19", they tried to demonstrate here the reasons of the differences of infection rate in countries with some have reduced cases and others not. According to them, the response efficacy of governmental intervention was conditioned by the community's reception, their perception and their action on the information provided by the government and other agencies. Despite the fact that there is not a one method communication, they tried in their study to bring out some recommendations for effective communication strategies to engender maximum support and participation from all groups. For them, effective communication implicates clear messages that are delivered via appropriate platforms, tailored for diverse audiences and transmitted or shared by people who are trusted by the different communities targeted. They outline that one of the main keys to long term success on developing and maintaining the public's trust. Equally, just as a diversity of community groups have to be included in

engagement activities; emerging digital technologies in communication and engagement activities have to be immersed. All of this draws us to understand that all communities have a role to play in the communication, the transmission of information concerning health issues such as Covid-19 and the important place of every group.

“How Covid-19 literacy influences fear, protective behavior and conspiracy beliefs among university students in Pakistan” published by (Naveed et al., 2023) was a research work instigated by the management of panic situations, the adoption of health preventive behaviors and adapting to new normal by the population. Its main objective was to examine the different effects of Covid-19 literacy on fear, protective behavior and conspiracy beliefs of university students. This study was a cross-sectional study done by an online questionnaire in two different universities from Lahore where a total of 301 responses were received and analyzed. Out of this analysis, it was demonstrated that, the existence of potential benefits of Covid-19 literacy to respond proactively to the fear caused by the pandemic, managing infodemic and adoption of health protective behaviors. It was observed that the university students with better Covid-19 literacy appeared to have less fear of Covid-19, and was more likely to adopt health-protective behaviors and believe less in conspiracy information. This proves that the good transmission of the right information by the right persons have a positive influence on the management of the pandemic among youths in universities.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

From the 15 articles that were been gotten for this research purpose, 10 of them were kept or used at the final stage. A thorough and critical reading of the articles was done and the different themes to be used were been gotten, as we were focused on those authors who have to bring a contribution to a non Covid-19 environment in different communities and in the world as a whole. The different articles that were finally kept had a great impact in the contribution of a non Covid-19 environment as all of them took into consideration the aspects of good communication strategies, mode of transmission of information, the management of infodemics, the importance of creating and having a good communication processes. Different governments, an author implicated in the management of this pandemic had his or her own way as communication strategies. But what was noted is that, communication via online debates, education and sensibilization of communities mostly on the terrain, projection of methods of good hygiene with pictures and videos, attractive posters with signs etc., were the main strategies of communication strategies.

Also, the role of media and ICT were taken into consideration by some authors, as (Alaa S Jameel et al., 2020) mentioned of the fact that, new technology is a good and appreciated way now our days to tackle situations when it comes to information to be transmitted since the means of communication makes it very simple and available to use. The different platforms of communication were also taken into consideration, as some are really used by a large number of individuals around the globe. Even the WHO, has taken this into consideration, in other to attained a good number of individuals, there making sure that information about the Covid-19 pandemic is gotten and in one way or the other, well communicated. Some of these platforms mentioned by some authors are; Facebook, Tweeter, Instagram, WhatsApp, Tencent and more again.

Government and political interventions in the management of particular situations in a country is of great importance as both parties do influence in all aspects. The management of the Covid-19 pandemic was seen to be of a success as the different parties including the communities had to take into consideration good communication strategies. Information given, as long as it goes in the right tract with what is going on will have a great role to play on individual perception.

Despite of the fact that, some authors mentioned the fact of reduced communication channels, family burnout, telemedicine, and reduced patient centered were some of the barriers of effective communication when it comes to physicians and patient care in the hospital base, the different

medium of communication has come to bring a bridge amount the barriers there by reducing all the risks and creating a more favorable environment.

CONCLUSION:

Information and communication are very important and serious for the proper management of situations. They play an important role the amelioration of situations as national and even international situations are concerned. In the case of pandemics, like the Covid-19, proper information and communication channels will accelerate the wellbeing and will lead to health promotion in one way or the other of individuals. A community that has proper information about a particular situation, where by a good communication process is put in place will be of a capital importance in their manner of viewing and taking the situation. This will give rise to a better understanding and hence promoting their health. The Covid-19 is a great example where we could see how information and communication are very important. Media, ICT through their different portals, with other platforms that are majorly used now our days are points to take into consideration to spread what a situation is all about to attained a good number of individuals.

Government should address new policies on the good use of different communicating platforms, medias in the proper management of situations especially those having a direct link with the health of individuals. What is to be known should be well informed and communicated in a proper manner. Covid-19 thought us a lot, and it should be noted that we all have a role to play for the improvement and management of situations, for an eventual growth.

REFERENCES

Alaa S Jameel, Abd Rhman Ahmad, & V Mohanned. (2020). *The Role of Information and Communication Technology on Knowledge Sharing among the Academic Staff during COVID-19 Pandemic | IEEE Conference Publication | IEEE Xplore.*

<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9408261>

Anwar, A., Malik, M., Raees, V., Anwar, A., Anwar, A., Malik, M., Raees, V., & Anwar, A. (2020). Role of Mass Media and Public Health Communications in the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Cureus, 12*(9). <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.10453>

B Venkatashiva Reddy & Arti Gupta. (2020). *Importance of effective communication during COVID-19 infodemic—PMC.* <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7586512/>

Calleja, N., AbdAllah, A., Abad, N., Ahmed, N., Albarracin, D., Altieri, E., Anoko, J. N., Arcos, R., Azlan, A. A., Bayer, J., Bechmann, A., Bezbaruah, S., Briand, S. C., Brooks, I., Bucci, L. M., Burzo, S., Czerniak, C., De Domenico, M., Dunn, A. G., ... Purnat, T. D. (2021). A Public Health Research Agenda for Managing Infodemics : Methods and Results of the First WHO Infodemiology Conference. *JMIR Infodemiology, 1*(1), e30979. <https://doi.org/10.2196/30979>

Elaine Wittenberg, Joy V. Goldsmith, & Chiahui chen. (2020). *Opportunities to improve COVID-19 provider communication resources : A systematic review—ScienceDirect.* <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0738399120306959>

Hyland-Wood, B., Gardner, J., Leask, J., & Ecker, U. K. H. (2021). Toward effective government communication strategies in the era of COVID-19. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications, 8*(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-020-00701-w>

Naveed, M. A., Shaukat, R., Asghar, A., & Rafique, G. M. (2023). How Covid-19 literacy influences fear, protective behaviour, and conspiracy beliefs among university students in Pakistan? *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 49(3), 102699.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2023.102699>

WHO. (2023). *WHO Coronavirus (Covid-19) Dashboard*. <https://covid19.who.int/table/>